

Kepler fits Compton

Adolf Cusmariu

adolcus@gmail.com

A photon bouncing at angle θ off a stationary electron undergoes unexpectedly a wavelength **increase** [1], the impact also recoiling the electron at angle ϕ ; see graphic below (photon in red, electron in blue).

After years of experiments and theoretical efforts to explain this increase, Compton derived the now-famous expression for the positive change $\Delta\lambda$ as

$$\Delta\lambda = \lambda(\theta) - \lambda_0 = \lambda_c(1 - \cos\theta)$$

where

θ = Photon bounce angle

λ_c = Compton wavelength of the Electron = 0.002426 nm

using some powerful modern physics; truly 'standing on the shoulders of giants', as Newton might say.

Now, given his angular data set

Deg = [0 45 90 135] (or in radians) **Rad = [0 0.7854 1.5708 2.3562]**

and the corresponding wavelength measurements (in nanometers)

Lam = [.0709 .0715 .0731 .0749]

what might Kepler have done to fit a model here, as he finally fit an **ellipse** through orbital measurements on the planet Mars; that is, to find a functional relationship between wavelength and angle:

Lam = f(Rad) ?

A simple plot of **wavelength vs. angle** isn't particularly suggestive (see below)

Although wavelengths corresponding to non-zero angular measurements appear to line up, there is no obvious functional dependence overall. After various false starts, Kepler might perhaps have stumbled on a way to linearize, by changing angles trigonometrically as

cos(Rad)

Then a plot of wavelength vs. cos(angle)

is promisingly linear indeed! Even better, **1 - cos(rad)** would make things positive and allow an easy estimate of slope (see plot below):

The intercept of this (almost) line is clearly $\text{Lam}(1) = 0.0709$. A model would now be available to Kepler as

$$\text{Lam} - \text{Lam}(1) = \text{Slope} * (1 - \text{cos}(\text{rad}))$$

And a Slope estimate would be easy:

$$\text{Slope} = \text{range}(\text{Lam}(2:4)) / \text{range}\{1 - \text{cos}(\text{Rad}(2:4))\} \approx \mathbf{.002404 \text{ nm}}$$

very close indeed to $\lambda_c = \mathbf{0.002426 \text{ nm}}$.

Of course, the physical meaning of this Slope would escape Kepler (we think).

[1] A. H. Compton, 'A Quantum Theory of the Scattering of X-Rays by Light Elements', Phys. Rev, 21, 1923.